

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE PROBLEM OF IMPLEMENTING OF CLIL POLICY IN THE CONTEXT OF LIFELONG EDUCATION IN KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

The given article is devoted to the issues of CLIL policy in the context of lifelong education in Kazakhstan. It is well-known that lifelong education refers to a certain constant, continuous improvement of knowledge, skills and habits of a person, associated with the need to be relevant in the modern professional and at the same time social environment. The review of scientific and pedagogical literature on the study of lifelong learning and CLIL policy is presented in the work. Furthermore, the authors dwell on the lesson plan using CLIL technology of the class conducted in Information Technologies Department for the 1st course students of Information Technologies educational program in Dulaty University.

Keywords: CLIL policy; lifelong education; technology; language integrated learning; personality

It is well-known that CLIL is a way of teaching academic subjects "through a foreign language" (teaching content through foreign language) and teaching a foreign language "through the subject itself" (teaching foreign language through content). CLIL assumes the duality of subject content and language learning. The term "lifelong education" has many meanings. First, lifelong education refers to a certain constant, continuous improvement of knowledge, skills and habits of a person, associated with the need to be relevant in the modern environment (professional, social). Secondly, this term refers to the system of views on the educational process as a whole. This system considers educational activities as an integral and fundamental component of a person's lifestyle at any age; it assumes the need to complete the educational ladder with new steps designed for all periods of a person's life. Third, lifelong education provides for the continuous enrichment of the creative potential of the individual, the development of a person as a creative person.

Nowadays, lifelong education is interpreted as a single system of state and public educational institutions, which ensures the organizational, substantive unity and continuity of all levels of education. The solution of the problems of education and training, professional training of a person should, on the one hand, take into account the current and future social needs, on the other hand, satisfy the desire of a person for self-education, versatile and harmonious development throughout life.

The origins of the idea of lifelong education can be found in the views of Confucius, Socrates, Aristotle, L. A. Seneca, Voltaire, J. V. Goethe, J. J. Rousseau, who associated them with the achievement of full development of a person as a personality. The first attempts to implement the idea of continuous education were made in the XIII-XIV centuries. In the cities of Europe on the basis of the so-called "workshop

schools", which were opened and maintained by craft workshops [1].

Yan Amos Komensky, the Czech humanist teacher, is considered to be the founder of modern ideas about lifelong education, his works contain the main idea that is currently reflected in the concept of lifelong education. The idea of continuity of education received new interpretations in the country after 1917, which was facilitated by the formation of a new education system. New forms and types of educational institutions have appeared, including those for adult education and professional development of the working population. However, by the end of the 60s of the XX century, the concept of lifelong education failed, and did not have time to become a central educational system. Appeals to this problem were based largely on the intuition of individual scientists and practitioners.

The term "lifelong education" was first used in 1968 in the UNESCO materials, and in 1972, a UNESCO decision was adopted that recognized lifelong education as the main principle, the "guiding structure" for innovations or reforms in education in all countries of the world. Currently, much attention is paid to the development of the system of lifelong education. Life puts forward its own requirements: to develop a person's ability to respond quickly to all changes, to take the initiative, to develop communication skills, etc. In a rapidly changing world, even a very good education may not be enough. The goal of education, related to the ability of a person to adapt to constantly changing living conditions, has changed. Gradually, "education for life" is replaced by "education through life" [2].

Indeed, lifelong education is a constant improvement of a person's knowledge and skills, caused by the need to "keep up with the times", the desire to be in demand in the existing professional and social environment. In addition, lifelong education is an important component of the interaction of science, economics and

education. The idea of lifelong education also emerged as a response to the dynamic changes in science and industry. In most countries of the world, it was associated with learning, and later with the need for personal development in the process of lifelong education [3].

The development of the system of lifelong education is one of the most important areas of educational activity, which implies the continuity of processes in the systems of preschool, general secondary, primary, secondary, higher, postgraduate and additional professional education. The effectiveness and possibility of educational activities are determined by the interrelationships between the various stages of the innovation cycle, producers and consumers of services; firms, the market, the state and other social partners. Lifelong education can be considered as part of the structure of "lifelong learning" [4].

The system of lifelong education is widespread all over the world. A modern person should not only have certain skills and abilities, but also be able to learn, constantly strive to enrich their knowledge, develop skills, find various sources of information, i.e. engage in self-education.

Self-education may include:

- obtaining a good secondary professional, higher professional education;
 - mastering foreign languages;
 - improvement of their cultural and technical level;
 - constant striving to obtain new skills and abilities, their rapid updating and replenishment;
 - improvement of such qualities as discipline, responsibility, initiative, creative approach to activity.
- Thus, the goal of lifelong education is not only to teach a person all his life, but also to teach him himself [5].

The components of the system of lifelong education are:

- educational programs;
- educational structures;
- financing and management mechanisms;
- social environment.

The system of lifelong education is aimed at the implementation of the following functions [6]:

- ensuring the adaptation of a person to the constantly changing conditions of not only professional activity, but also the social environment by providing opportunities for the organization of an individual educational trajectory throughout life;
- strengthening, combining the educational resources of the society;
- formation of educational social partnership as a component of civil society.

Lifelong learning refers to the process of gaining knowledge and learning new skills throughout your life. Many people continue their education for personal development and fulfillment, while others see it as a significant step toward career advancement [7].

The change of the paradigm of "lifelong education" to "lifelong learning" has revealed a new concept for the Republic of Kazakhstan – "lifelong learning". The content of this term is perceived by many ambiguously, and there are several reasons for this. On the one hand, it is associated with the three – level training system "bachelor – master - doctoral", the transition

to which was carried out in the national educational system of the republic within the framework of the Bologna process. This system is focused both on the assignment of qualifications (bachelor's degree), and on the award of academic (master's degree) and academic degrees (doctoral degree) in accordance with the established procedure. With its introduction, the process of obtaining education has become multi-level (pre-university, university and postgraduate training), multi-stage (school, college, university, master's degree, doctoral degree) and continuous-in the literal sense of the word [8].

According to the typology proposed by UNESCO, this type of lifelong education is usually called formal, that is, provided by special educational institutions, according to established standards, with the involvement of specially trained personnel.

In our republic, there is an obvious trend of an increasing role of enterprises in financing the professional development of their employees (usually through the organization of corporate training seminars), which is more due to commercial interests than to such a concept as "social responsibility of business". The degree of state participation in the financing of non-formal lifelong education is limited by tax benefits, which are not of significant interest to business.

Today, along with information and communication competence, multiculturalism is recognized by the global education community as one of the main directions in the field of education in the formation of a competent and global educational space. In the 90s, within the framework of the policy of multilingual development in Europe, the CLIL method was developed. The role of information and Communication Technologies is constantly increasing. The formation of key competencies is facilitated by training in English, conducted using the CLIL method (Content Language Integrated Learning). The peculiarity of this method of teaching is that in different teaching situations, classes are conducted in two languages (domestic and foreign) using the appropriate language for a given period of study and learning goals.

The main goal of the CLIL method is to reduce the teacher's speech and, on the contrary, develop students' ability to communicate with each other.

Content (content) – knowledge, business, skills in the subject area that form information competence, i.e. the skills and ability to independently search, analyze, select, process and transmit the necessary information [9];

Communication - teaching a language that offers additional use of foreign language knowledge, rather than learning a foreign language in the classroom, so that students use a foreign language when learning, as well as learn how to use it. This aspect forms communicative competencies, as the ability to listen, ask questions and formulate clear answers to them, listen carefully and actively discuss the issues under consideration, understand the opinion of your partner and give them a critical assessment develops the ability of personal language communication;

Cognition – develops cognitive and thinking skills and contributes to the formation of educational competencies that ensure good training of students in one or more areas of study [10].

Culture - an aspect of the development of general cultural competence by means of knowledge of the world, presenting itself as a part of Culture, Understanding and perception of an alternative culture, ensuring the assimilation of the language of culture.

Thus, conducting in English using the CLIL method provides meta subject connections and allows you to achieve practical results in the development of the principles of a new educational standard, in particular, develops cultural awareness, internationalization, language competence, not only readiness to study, but also the ability to apply new knowledge in life and, accordingly, increase life motivation, achieve the goal of success, and ultimately the main goal – it leads to the formation of professional competencies of future graduates, increasing their mobility and ability to adapt to rapidly changing life situations [11].

The development of professional competence of teachers is a tool for improving the quality of Education. In modern society, where science and technology are developed, the education system requires competitive specialists with developed professional competencies. For this purpose, there is a need for subject – specific integration in the training process in accordance with the requirements of the time. That is, CLIL technology is one of the main ways to solve this problem.

We are going to show a lesson plan using CLIL technology (conducted in Information Technologies Department in Dulat University, 1st course)

Course «Communication network installations»

Lesson topic: Reliability of communication routes. End-to-end cable installations. End installations of coaxial cable

Lesson type – theory, component lesson

The aim of the lesson:

- a) Educational – to check the students' knowledge on the subject, the ability to use student's knowledge effectively and readily in execution

- b) Developmental – to improve students' responsibility, knowledge, develop the right attitude to life, thinking development, study carefully the general public

Method of lesson: presentation, interpretation, interviews, lectures elements, question-and-answer, development, approval, repeat.

Visual aids and technical equipment: Interactive whiteboards, books, handouts, samples

Procedure of the lesson

Organization moment:

- a) Greeting with students
- b) Checking up the attendance
- c) Paying attention to the readiness of the classroom

Introducing with the first slide

Plan

1. To divide into groups (to divide the with the method of construction, assembling the pieces of the pictures, assessment worksheet)

2. Home task (group, individual work)

3. Defining the content (new theme, picture, Video)

4. Assessment

5. Meditation (poster)

6. Reflection

7. Home task

Progress:

1. Homework: Safety of fiber optic cables from various obstacles

List of references:

1. Nietaliev Zh. Zh. "Ways of communication", 2017

2. Belorussov N. I. "Electrical cables and wires". M, "Energy", 2019

Familiarization of students with the system of scoring points based on achievement criteria.

According to the homework:

Group work (working in a group, analyzing the progress of work, sharing and performing tasks with solidarity, be responsible)	3 scores
Opening a topic based on this image	1 score
Answer on behalf of the group on a given task (leader)	3 scores
Show activity in a group	
1 token	1 score
2 tokens	2 scores
3 tokens	3 scores
4 tokens	4 scores
5 tokens	5 scores
Individual work	
Answer test questions	
To 5 questions	
To 4 questions	
To 3 questions	
To 2 questions	
To 1 question	

Checklist:

Number of points by Criterion					Score	Grade
	Full name of the student	A	B	C		
1	Omar Serik					
2	Mustafa Aruzhan					
3	Omirezak Moldir					
4	Akbay Amina					
5	Nursultan Diana					
6	Abdenbay Madiyar					
7	Zaripulla Mukhtar					

Converting points to grades:

Number of points scored	Grade
17 – 20	“5”
13 – 16	“4”
10 - 12	“3”

Assessment: Evaluation according to the point system

Recognition of meaning: A new lesson

Topic: Reliability of communication routes. End-to-end cable installations. End installations of coaxial cable.

Plan:

1. Capacity of communication lines	1. Жолдардың өткізу қабілеті
2. subscriber cable devices: Kroos, box, plinth	2. Абоненттік кабель: Кроос, бокс, плинтус
3. coaxial cable	3. Коаксиалды кабель
4. types of coaxial cables	4. Коаксиалды кабельдердің түрлері

Working with the copybook: term words, abbreviated words

List of references: Nietalieva Zh. Zh."Ways of communication", 2017

Video: Ways to use coaxial cables

Thinking: The poster is made according to the method of protection

Progress: Protection of the project by each group on the specified illustrated topics

Project topics for groups:

Kroos	5 scores
Boxing	5 scores
Plinth	5 scores
Cable	5 scores
Project protection by poster method	5 scores

Assessment: Calculating the number of points for tokens

Reflection: Feedback (What did we learn? What did we know? What do I want to know?)

Homework assignment

If so, the most effective way to implement an integrated educational program is to learn English. Learning English is a huge task and responsibility for all of us.

Conclusion

The content of school teacher training using the CLIL methodology should not be limited solely to teaching a foreign language, but should include theoretical and methodological aspects necessary for the effective integration of new language material and subject content within the framework of one lesson.

Coming to the conclusion, we want to say that teaching English with the help of CLIL technology is not only relevant now but also it provides us opportunities to introduce a wide range of cultural contexts to help students develop positive attitudes and become aware of the responsibilities of global as well as local citizenship.

CLIL unites language teachers and subject teachers. CLIL helps students discover and develop multiple skills - so-called pluriliteracy skills.

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